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**An in-silico insight into the selenium metabolism by methionine S-methyltransferase
contributing fungal disease resistance in plants**

*Piyush Ghoshe¹, Arti Shanware², Shweta Nandanwar^{3,†}, Rashmi Wanjari¹, Lalit
Kharbikar^{1,*}*

¹ICAR – National Institute of Biotic Stress Management, Raipur - 493 225, India.

²Rajiv Gandhi Biotechnology Centre, RTM Nagpur University, Nagpur – 440 010, India.

³Harper Adams University, Newport, Shropshire – TF10 8NB, United Kingdom.

[†]Resigned.

Email: lalitkharbikar@gmail.com

Selenium is an essential micronutrient that enhances the fungal disease resistance in plants when available at lower levels; however, at higher levels, the micronutrient shows toxic effects. Hence, plants have evolved a methionine S-methyltransferase (*MSMT*)-based mechanism that metabolizes selenium into selenoamino acid to regulate the availability of this micronutrient at precise levels. Using data-mining tools the regulatory roles of *MSMT* in selenoamino acid metabolism have been characterized in the present study. Phylogenetic analysis showed a wide distribution of different protein derivatives, closely linked to *MSMT*, across the plant species studied. Three conserved domains of *MSMT* were found at variable positions across all the homologous protein sequences analyzed through motif-based sequence analysis tools (MEME Suite). Nine transcription factor binding sites, involved in various fundamental biological, cellular and molecular functions, could be identified in *MSMT* through gene ontology (GO) analysis. Various plant small RNA target sites identified in *MSMT* suggest that it plays a crucial role in post-transcriptional modifications of the selenoamino acid metabolism pathway. This is the first report on in-silico characterization of functional, regulatory and structural properties of *MSMT* concerning the metabolism of selenium into selenoamino acid. Further, the study suggests that *MSMT* can be manipulated to enhance the fungal disease resistance in plants.